

Policy Brief: Transitioning to a safe and sustainable circular economy for plastics

The transition to a circular economy minimizes resource consumption and plastic pollution by moving away from the current linear economic model. The transition to a sustainable circular economy should focus on reducing production and consumption, and only secondly increase recycling rates, because large investments in waste handling facilities will promote the expanded production of waste due to technology lock-in. What is more, this is bound to occur at the cost of waste prevention and plastic reuse. In addition, unavoidable waste must be utilized more efficiently. Further, chemicals in plastics must be given sufficient attention, as hazardous chemicals are barriers to safe and transparent material preservation. Indeed, recycled and/or reused plastics may contain higher levels of hazardous chemicals than virgin plastics. Finally, reducing the overall volume of plastics introduced into the economy decreases unintended and unavoidable releases into the environment (including from micro- and nanoplastics and plastic chemicals).

What is the circular economy?

There are at least 114 different definitions of the circular economy [1], but in principle, a circular economy models its material flows on nature's self-regenerating closed loops of materials and chemical elements. In the circular economy, materials are kept in the value chain for as long as possible before they become waste, and this waste then becomes input for other processes. Ultimately, the circular economy becomes a continuous development cycle that sustainably meets human needs while optimizing resource utilization, thereby reducing environmental degradation, by becoming a restorative and regenerative system [2, 3]. Materials are designed primarily for longevity and reuse, and also for subsequent recycling, although currently there is an over-emphasis on plastics recycling [4, 5].

What are the principles for a safer circular economy for plastics?

- I. Support the minimisation, safety and sustainability of plastic production**
 - Minimize plastics consumption [6].
 - Cap overall global polymer production (including soluble polymers) [7, 8].
 - Establish controls on the design, production, and use of polymers and related substances of concern based on safety and sustainability criteria [9, 10].
 - Develop mandatory and standardized labeling, tracking, and reporting of polymers [11, 12].
 - Avoid large-scale investments in waste handling facilities (such as chemical recycling) that promote the continued production of plastics waste due to technology lock-ins at the cost of waste prevention and plastic reuse [13-15].

- II. Ensure safety and sustainability of plastic products across their lifecycle**
 - Identify societally essential and non-essential uses of plastics, inspired by the “essential-use” concept [16, 17].
 - Mandate the redesign of plastic products for essential uses to keep them reused safely in the value chain for as long as possible [18].

- Require that the chemicals associated with all life stages of plastics, including non-intentionally added substances present in finished products, are known [19] and that they are tested for hazards (including endocrine disruption) using best available science [20, 21], and properly managed to minimize risk to human health and the environment.
- Establish criteria for material reuse and recycling that ensure safety and sustainability, including minimizing generation and leakage of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) into the environment throughout the entire life cycle [4], and improving material inertness [22, 23].
- Restrict the use of plastics which over their lifetime will shed MNPs ensuring human exposures (such as in potable water delivery) and test health and environmental effects of MNPs [24, 25].

III. Design rights-based, safe, and sustainable systems

- Incentivise restorative and regenerative circular materials and zero waste systems [26] including safe and sustainable reuse and the right to repair [27].
- Ensure the sourcing and use of materials and supportive systems are rights-based and adequately assessed for safety and sustainability [28].
- Ensure just transitions away from the unsafe handling of waste (especially child labor used for waste picking) to new materials and distribution systems [29].
- Evaluate legacy plastics carefully and separately for their inclusion in the circular economy, for example due to the presence of hazardous chemicals, to ensure safe and transparent material preservation [30].
- Create awareness for and minimize rebound effects (i.e. unintended consequences of single-issue focus solutions), considering Jevons Paradox [31] and lessons learned from regrettable substitutions [32].

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References

1. Kirchherr, J., D. Reike, and M. Hekkert, *Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions*. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 2017. **127**: p. 221-232.
2. Morsetto, P., *Restorative and regenerative: Exploring the concepts in the circular economy*. Journal of Industrial Ecology, 2020. **24**(4): p. 763-773.
3. Foundation, E.M., *Towards the circular economy Vol. 2: opportunities for the consumer goods sector*. 2013.

4. Rosenberg Johansen, M., et al., *A review of the plastic value chain from a circular economy perspective*. Journal of Environmental Management, 2022. **302**: p. 113975.
5. Dörnyei, K.R., et al., *Sustainable food packaging: An updated definition following a holistic approach*. Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems, 2023. **7**.
6. Ramos, T., et al., *Reducing plastic in the operating theatre: Towards a more circular economy for medical products and packaging*. Journal of Cleaner Production, 2023. **383**: p. 135379.
7. Bauer, F., et al., *Plastics and climate change: Breaking carbon lock-ins through three mitigation pathways*. One Earth, 2022. **5**(4): p. 361-376.
8. Simon, N., et al., *A binding global agreement to address the life cycle of plastics*. Science, 2021. **373**(6550): p. 43-47.
9. Patinha Caldeira, C., et al., *Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials Review of safety and sustainability dimensions, aspects, methods, indicators, and tools*. 2022, European Commission Joint Research Centre: Publications Office of the European Union.
10. Groh, K.J., et al., *Assessing and managing environmental hazards of polymers: historical development, science advances and policy options*. Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts, 2023. **25**(1): p. 10-25.
11. Simon, F. *EU's upcoming 'digital product passport' will include packaging, official says*. 2023; Available from: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/energy-environment/news/eus-upcoming-digital-product-passport-will-also-include-packaging-official-says/>.
12. De Hoe, G.X., T. Şucu, and M.P. Shaver, *Sustainability and Polyesters: Beyond Metals and Monomers to Function and Fate*. Accounts of Chemical Research, 2022. **55**(11): p. 1514-1523.
13. Blumenthal, J., et al., *Time to Break the "Lock-In" Impediments to Chemicals Management*. Environ Sci Technol, 2022. **56**(7): p. 3863-3870.
14. Davidson, M.G., R.A. Furlong, and M.C. McManus, *Developments in the life cycle assessment of chemical recycling of plastic waste – A review*. Journal of Cleaner Production, 2021. **293**: p. 126163.
15. Syberg, K., *Beware the false hope of recycling*. nature, 2022. **611**(S6).
16. Cousins, I.T., et al., *The concept of essential use for determining when uses of PFASs can be phased out*. Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts, 2019. **21**(11): p. 1803-1815.
17. Cousins, I.T., et al., *Finding essentiality feasible: common questions and misinterpretations concerning the "essential-use" concept*. Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts, 2021. **23**(8): p. 1079-1087.
18. Katakajwala, R., et al., *Circular Economy Induced Resilience in Socio-Ecological Systems: an Ecological Perspective*. Materials Circular Economy, 2023. **5**.
19. United Nations Environment Programme and Secretariat of the Basel Rotterdam and Stockholm Conventions, *Chemicals in plastics: a technical report*. 2023, UNEP.
20. Schug, T.T., et al., *Designing endocrine disruption out of the next generation of chemicals*. Green Chemistry, 2013. **15**(1): p. 181-198.
21. European Commission. *Chemical testing: new safety test methods approved*. 2023; Available from: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/chemical-testing-new-safety-test-methods-approved-2023-03-03_en.
22. Geueke, B., et al., *Hazardous chemicals in recycled and reusable plastic food packaging*. Cambridge Prisms: Plastics, 2023: p. 1-43.
23. Muncke, J., L. Zimmermann, and J.M. Boucher. *Feedback from: Food Packaging Forum Foundation. Have your say*. 2023 [cited 2023; Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12263-Reducing-packaging-waste-review-of-rules/F3407283_en].
24. Xu, J.-L., et al., *A review of potential human health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics exposure*. Science of The Total Environment, 2022. **851**: p. 158111.
25. Castiello, F., et al., *Exposure to non-persistent pesticides and sexual maturation of Spanish adolescent males*. Chemosphere, 2023. **324**: p. 138350.
26. Connett, P., *The Zero Waste Solution. Unrashing the Planet One Community at a Time*. 2013: Chelsea Green Publishing.
27. Blumhardt, H. and L. Prince, *From lines to circles: reshaping waste policy*. Policy Quarterly, 2022. **18**(2).
28. Pachauri, A., et al., *Safe and sustainable waste management of self care products*. Bmj, 2019. **365**: p. l1298.
29. Schroeder, P. and J. Barrie, *Is going circular just? Environmental justice and just transition – key elements for an inclusive circular economy*. Field Actions Science Reports, 2022(Special Issue 24): p. 20-25.
30. Greenpeace, *Forever Toxic: the science on health threats from plastic recycling*. 2023.
31. Alcott, B., *Jevons' paradox*. Ecological Economics, 2005. **54**(1): p. 9-21.
32. Parkinson, L.V. *Regrettable substitution & the precautionary principle*. 2022; Available from: <https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/food-packaging-health/regrettable-substitution-the-precautionary-principle>.